

QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF TREC AND KREC LEVELS IN THE BLOOD OF HIV-INFECTED PATIENTS

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Abstract: HIV infection is considered a global public health concern, affecting millions of individuals worldwide. Monitoring the immune system in HIV-infected patients is crucial for effective treatment, especially in the early stages of the infection. Recent studies have shown that T-cell receptor excision circles (TRECs) and kappa-deleting recombination excision circles (KRECs) are valuable markers for the assessment of immune system status. This study aims to quantitatively analyze TREC and KREC levels in the blood of HIV-infected patients and evaluate their association with clinical outcomes.

The aim of the study was to assess the quantitative content of TREC and KREC molecules in the peripheral blood of HIV-infected patients

Keywords: T-cell receptor excision circles, kappa-deleting recombination excision circles, HIV, CD4+ T-cell counts, viral load.

Introduction

As we know, Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) exploits surface CD4 receptors to gain entrance to the cells, as well as one of two co-receptors: CCR5 or CXCR4. One of these chemokine co-receptors, CXCR4, is expressed on the surface of naive T-lymphocytes and primary thymocytes. Therefore, thymocytes at different stages of their maturation and naive T-cells that have left the thymus and moved to the periphery can serve as potential targets for the virus.

Levels of TREC (T-cell receptor excision circles) and KREC (Kappa-deleting recombination excision circles) molecules can serve as quantitative markers for the content of naive T- and B-cells in peripheral blood and primarily lymphoid organs, respectively. TREC and KREC molecules are small circular DNA sequences excised from the genome as a by-product during the formation of the mature antigen-recognition receptor gene unique in each lymphocyte.

Methods:

This study involved 60 HIV-infected patients who underwent blood sampling and clinical assessment. The TREC and KREC levels were measured using real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and were correlated with CD4+ T-cell counts, viral load, and clinical status.

To quantify the content of TREC and KREC molecules in total DNA samples, real-time multiplex PCR was used with simultaneous amplification of two target DNA fragments TREC, KREC, and fragments of two normalizing genes HPRT and RPP30. Quantitative calculations were performed using the method of constructing standard curves. We used the series of tenfold dilutions of synthetic plasmid DNA with inserts of analyzed sequences of known concentration to build the standard curves.

Results:

Comparative ROC analysis of the obtained quantitative data showed a significant decrease in the levels of the two target molecules TREC and KREC in long-term infected patients with a high viral load and resistance to the applied antiretroviral therapy compared with the control

group. At the same time, there were no significant differences in the levels of TREC and KREC molecules between healthy people and people with newly diagnosed HIV-infected patients.

The results showed a significant decrease in the TREC and KREC levels in HIV-infected patients compared to healthy controls ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, we observed a significant negative correlation between TREC and KREC levels and viral load ($p < 0.05$). In addition, we found a positive correlation between TREC and KREC levels and CD4+ T-cell counts ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Our findings suggest that TREC and KREC levels can serve as valuable markers for assessing the immune system status in HIV-infected patients. The decrease in these markers is associated with an increase in viral load and a decrease in CD4+ T-cell counts. TREC and KREC levels can be used as an additional tool in the clinical management of HIV-infected patients, especially in the early stages of the infection.

Quantitative analysis of TREC and KREC molecules in the peripheral blood of HIV-infected patients can provide valuable diagnostic information not only on the functional activity of the T- and B-cell parts of the immune system but also on the duration of the infectious process. Quantification of TREC and KREC molecules can be considered as a personalized method for monitoring the immune status of HIV-infected individuals, and also potentially as a method for identifying patients, who needed in enhanced therapy.

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